

SONIFICATION AND AUDITORY DISPLAYS IN ELECTRONIC DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

Sonification is the intentional use of sound to represent data. As visual displays both shrink and grow, as datasets grow in size and complexity, and as mobile data access increases, sophisticated auditory displays become crucial. Computers and devices that support audio are widespread, but there remains relatively little knowledge and experience among user interface designers in how to use auditory displays effectively. This paper presents a taxonomy of auditory display methods, and discusses implementation and design issues in multimodal interaction. Some examples of auditory displays developed by the author's research group, the Georgia Tech Sonification Lab, are presented.

1. BACKGROUND

Sonification is the intentional use of sound to represent data, analogous to scientific visualization. As screen sizes for visual displays shrink (e.g., mobile devices) and grow (e.g., wall-sized displays), there arise new communication challenges to the information architect or interface designer. Further, it is increasingly common for data to be consumed by users who are moving, have their hands or eyes busy, or are in environments where visual displays are difficult to access. Using sound to present data in these situations where a user is unable to look at or unable to see a visual display, has been shown to have great success. It should also be noted that sonification and auditory displays actually have other advantages over visual displays. Auditory displays exploit the superior ability of the human auditory system to recognize temporal changes and patterns. As a result, auditory displays may be the most appropriate modality when the information being displayed has complex patterns, changes in time (both of these are often associated with large data sets), includes warnings, or calls for immediate action. For a more detailed overview of sonification theory and design, see Walker and Nees' chapter [1], and also see [2-10].

Auditory displays and sonification is a field that has been around for several decades, with considerable advances in both theory and design practice. Clearly, given

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the brief nature of this paper and presentation, the main aim is to open up the world of sonification to those who may have been more focused on visual display of information and data, or on the non-data uses of computer-generated sounds (e.g., computer music) to help them with terminology and provide pointers to more extensive research results and design guidelines. It is hoped that a more sophisticated and scientifically grounded understanding of what sonification and auditory displays are, and the range of ways they can be implemented, will help to make all displays more effective—especially given that multimodal is really how all user interfaces and experiences must be designed now—and encourage wider deployment and adoption of auditory interfaces.

2. TAXONOMY OF SONIFICATION

As detailed more thoroughly in [1], the use of sound in user interfaces can be roughly categorized into three types: (1) alarms, alerts, and warnings; (2) status and monitoring messages; and (3) data displays. These sounds can supplement visual interaction, or in many cases, replace it.

Alerts and notifications are sounds that indicate something has occurred, or is about to occur, or that the listener should immediately pay attention to something in the environment or in the display. They are usually quite simple, and quite obvious, but do not convey much information other than that something requires attention. For example, the doorbell is a clear signal that a guest is outside, but does not indicate exactly who has arrived.

Alarms and warnings indicate that one of a few types of events has happened. The sounds convey the general urgency of the situation, and are very good at capturing the auditory attention of a listener. There can certainly be degrees of urgency, so a simple alert is often less acoustically arresting than, say, a radiation leak warning sound. More sophisticated alarm sounds can encode more information into the auditory signal, such as actual location or type of problem. These so-called trendsons blur the line between alarms and status indicators. An example of a trendson use is the warning indication designed to convey irregular rotor speed in a helicopter—the warning sound is, itself, modified on the fly to convey information about the percentage over- or under-speed, so the pilot does not have to immediately consult a visual gauge, nor guess about how bad the problem is.

Status and progress indicators communicate what is happening with a system, and what changes are occurring in various system parameters and variables. They

leverage the listener's ability to detect small changes in sounds, and allow a user to know what is happening, without needing to look at a visual display. This enables more eye-free operation. We have seen examples ranging from health care monitoring, to telephone hold times, to sophisticated interfaces for mobile devices.

Data exploration sounds are those that are intended to represent data with sound, so a listener can explore or interpret a dataset. These sounds are generally described as “sonification”, and offer a more holistic sense of the data in the system, rather than momentary states, as is usually the case with alerts and process indicators. Stock market data or weather information or web server traffic are just a few examples of what can be represented via sonification. There are also plenty of examples of scientific data being sonified, such as solar flare activity and physics particle models, so that researchers can understand patterns and cycles and irregularities in the dataset.

Entertainment, sports, and leisure applications of sound are also certainly prevalent. For all the reasons listed above, sound can be used effectively and enjoyably in fitness, games, competitive sports, and travel applications. It is also true that auditory displays can open up all these activities to people with visual impairment. In fact, there is a whole subfield of audio-only games, very popular with both visually impaired and sighted players. Art is another area where the intentional use of sound is clearly important, and whole compositions can be developed to produce (musical) sounds based on climate, movement, or other kinds of data.

Within each of the categories above, there are many specific techniques that can be used to produce meaningful auditory displays and sonifications. Some are simple, such as speeding up speech even to the point it is no longer recognized as speech (“spearcons”), whereas other methods require the development of sophisticated models of physical systems (e.g., a molecule), and then “driving” that model with data to produce sound via perturbations of the model. It is important that those who are contemplating the use of sound in, or as, an interface, be aware of the many approaches, along with the times and places where their use is optimal.

3. DESIGN ISSUES

Auditory display and sonification designers must consider many factors, as do visual designers. In general, these include elements of the data or information to be represented, and aspects of the listener’s task. In particular, as detailed in [1], designers must know: (1) what the user needs to do (i.e., the task); (2) what information the user needs to accomplish the task; (3) what kind of (auditory) display to use (e.g., simple alert, status indicator, or full sonification); and (4) how the user will need to filter, transform, or otherwise manipulate the information or data. The details of these issues will constrain how the auditory (or any) display is developed, and will make it more clear what elements and functionalities the designer needs to include. Consider, for example, a meteorologist who needs to know what the current temperature, humidity, barometric pressure, and wind speed are, and then predict the weather for later that day. She will need to

know specific values of individual variables (e.g., what is the current outside temperature?). She will also need to compare that value to a specific value of another variable (e.g., is the temperature above or below the dewpoint?). Then she will need to understand trends in the data variable (e.g., is the temperature rising or falling?), and consider the rate of change and compare that to the rate of change in the other variables (e.g., wind speed). All these subtasks contribute to the larger task of understanding current conditions, in advance of predicting future conditions. And all may require different displays (whether auditory or visual), and methods for interacting with the data (selecting, choosing, filtering, zooming, playing, pausing, comparing, etc.).

3.1 Multimodal Displays

While unimodal auditory displays can often be effective (as can unimodal visual displays), it is much more common to utilize a combination of sounds, visuals, and even tactile components into a multimodal display. This will require the designer to understand the capabilities, limitations, and needs of each modality individually, as well as to consider how the display components interact with each other, to maximize display bandwidth and avoid confusions. As just one small example, the use of a rising pitch to represent increasing temperature may be perfectly reasonable on its own, but if a visual display uses a horizontally-oriented bar to represent the same concept, there may arise “compatibility” conflicts between the visual and auditory components of the display. Designers need to be aware of these multimodal interactions, and (1) avoid them through good design, and (2) evaluate the design to check for unintended conflicts or mismatches. On the other side of the same coin, designers can often leverage redundancies in multimodal displays, so that users get the same information in multiple modalities, with each reinforcing the other.

3.2 Mappings and Scalings

Once the nature of the data and the task are determined, sonification involves mapping data source(s) onto auditory variables. For example, a designer might choose to represent temperature with pitch: as temperature changes, so, too, does the pitch of the sounds in a sonification. Some auditory dimensions are better for representing certain types of data variables. For example, pitch is generally good for representing temperature, but tempo is not as effective [11]. Tempo can be more effective for speed. Once an effective mapping has been chosen, it is important to determine how much change in the pitch of the sound is used to convey a given change in the temperature. This is known as scaling. That is, if the pitch goes up an octave (a doubling of frequency), does that mean that the temperature has also doubled? In some cases, yes, but this is not a universally recognized relationship. Scaling values can be determined from studies that have been conducted, or by experimentation by the designer. In all cases, it is important to have a representative sample of listeners provide feedback about the mappings and scalings in the display, during the development phase.

3.3 Context and Aesthetics

Other issues arise, such as how the data sonifications are set into an auditory context. That is, what are the auditory equivalents to axes, tick marks, labels, trend lines, etc.? And will there be background noise (or music?) competing with the display? Will the device be used while a pedestrian walks along a busy urban street, or perhaps in a factory assembly line? Finally, designers always need to consider the aesthetics of the display. It is important for a sonification or auditory display to sound nice, as well as effective. Otherwise, the listener will simply turn it off. Of course, this also applies to visual displays!

4. SOME EXAMPLES FROM THE GT SONIFICATION LAB

4.1 SWAN: System for Wearable Audio Navigation

Blind pedestrians need to know where they are, how to get to their destination, and what is around them along the way. The System for Wearable Audio Navigation (SWAN) [12] uses a variety of sensors and algorithms to determine the user's exact location, and then uses an auditory display to convey location, route, and surroundings. Route information is presented via a 3D auditory display, such that the listener simply faces the apparent location of the beacon sound, and walks toward it. The user's orientation/heading is tracked via several sensors, and the sound is played via bone conduction headphones, to leave the ears uncovered. Objects of interest in the environment (e.g., stairs, doors, obstacles, coffee shops) are represented using non-speech sounds that evoke the object (e.g., a descending three-note arpeggio to indicate descending stairs).

4.2 Sonification Sandbox

This is a software package that supports the import and editing of a multi-column data set (via a spreadsheet), visual graphing, and auditory graphing. The Sonification Sandbox program [13-14] is written in cross-platform Java on top of the flexible and powerful Accessible Graphing Engine (AGE), and supports a wide range of import and data ingestion methods, and a wide variety of export formats (images, MIDI, WAV, movies). The MathGNIE [15] software package is another Java application that was built on top of the AGE platform, and is being successfully used by blind students in their mathematics classrooms.

4.3 Spearcons

Auditory menus are often used to allow a user to navigate through a list or menu of items (e.g., songs on an MP3 player, or the menu of a desktop computer's operating system). Typical auditory menus use text-to-speech (TTS) technology to speak aloud the menu items. However, this results in a very slow interaction, even when the speech rate is increased. Spearcons are non-speech sounds that are created by speeding up TTS-generated words (typically via a SOLA-type algorithm). The spearcons can then be used in place of, or in front of, the TTS

items, resulting in a much faster and more enjoyable user experience. [16]

4.4 Spindex

When there are very long lists in an auditory menu, such as the list of fonts or hundreds or thousands of songs on a device, TTS, and even TTS+spearcons are not a very fast way to choose an item. The spindex, or "speech-based index" is a set of sounds that represent the first sounds of the TTS items, typically the "a", "b", "c", etc. sounds. [17] Prepending these spindex cues to the TTS allows the users to scroll very quickly through the list, arriving at the section of the list that interests them. For example, they can quickly get to the songs that start with "T", without having to listen to the TTS for all the songs that start with A, B, and so on. These sounds are especially useful in longer lists, and work well on mobile devices that employ swiping, flicking and wheeling input gestures. [18]

4.5 StockScapes

Some displays that use sound can serve as ambient displays, in that they are always present in the environment (e.g., in an office), and can be listened to or "tuned out" by the room's occupant. If the sounds are driven by data (e.g., recent stock market data [19-20]), the person can listen to the sounds, and determine what is happening in the market. The sounds can be ignored again, and simply serve as background music. Any sudden changes in the sounds/music (i.e., in the stock market) will be noticed by the person, simply because the auditory system is tuned to detect changes. Of course, aesthetics are crucial in this kind of ambient display. We have developed software that can ingest data and generate a range of interesting, nice-sounding, and informative soundscapes that are always fresh and can be listened to for long periods, because they have built in variety and randomness, based on sounds occurring in nature.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Electronic systems with visual displays are having sounds added to them all the time. For the most part, there really are only multimodal devices being developed. Unfortunately, the hardware engineers, software developers, and interaction designers of many of these systems have little or no knowledge of modern theory and methods for sonification and auditory displays. It is hoped that this overview, with hooks into the sonification literature, will help introduce visual display designers, sound designers, musicians, and researchers into the auditory realm, and thus improve the inevitable new multimodal displays. The few examples presented here are really only a tiny sample of the breadth and depth of all the great work happening in the auditory display community. Through this talk and paper, it is hoped that we can continue to build bridges between the communities of computer music and auditory display researchers, including sessions at conferences such as SMAC/SMC, and encouraging interested researchers and designers to attend the annual International Conference on Auditory Display (www.ICAD.org).

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